

ARCHIVE: The national archives in Hämeenlinna (Janakkalan tuomiokunnan arkisto, Hämeenlinnan maakunta-arkisto)

FULL ARCHIVAL REFERENCE: The archives of the municipal court of Loppi, The national archives in Hämeenlinna

PERSONS: -

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF CONTENT: Court records, statistics, indictment letters etc material provided by the regional court.

PERSON VISITING ARCHIVE: Ville Erkkilä

DATE VISITED: Summer 2021

DATE TRANSCRIBED: 4.11.2025

OTHER DOCUMENTATION: -

KNOWN REFERENCES IN LITERATURE: Ville Erkkilä. Rural (In)Justice: Smallholding as Social Policy in Modernizing Finland, from 1945 to the 1960s. In Experiencing society and the Lived Welfare State. Edited by Pertti Haapala, Minna Harjula and Heikki Kokko. Palgrave Macmillan, 2023.

RESTRICTIONS OF USE: -

NOTES ON THE ARCHIVAL SOURCE:

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